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4. Any other immoral, offensive, comments, or comments against any established custom or culture.

OBJECTIVES

1. To provide a platform for Indian Legal Professionals including Judges, Academicians, Advocates, and Students for showcasing their research skills;
2. To build an endeavor of research and analytical altitude amongst the young legal professionals under the experience and guidance of the senior legal experts;
3. To highlight the possible developments needed in the area of law through research and analytical spirits;
4. To encourage the habit of critical analysis and argumentative behavior amongst the law students; and
5. To help in policy formulation and legal drafting in India by expressing suggestions brought forward through research skills.

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BOOK REVIEW ON JUDICIARY, JUDGES AND ADMINISTRATION OF JUSTICE

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In this book J. R Banumati has dealt with many connected their research to problems faced by the imperative aspects and issues which have bothered Indian judiciary.

the Judiciary, judges, and administration of justice. Under this book not only issues are discussed but All such impediments and how do they affect the also remedies which our courts can take to finally judiciary are dealt with by the author in great detail settle them. For instance issue of docket explosion is as well as how law and principles of equity can be not only dealt with but also J. Banumathi writes what used as efficient tools to overcome such hindrances steps Apex court has taken and what others are left to causing grave injustice to the general public. be implemented to resolve huge pendency of suits. In

The author throws light in the first part of the book part II she writes about the E-Courts project and its on precept and postulates directly related to the communication and technology enablement of court Indian judiciary. Part I contains a discussion on and right to information act,2005. She has referred to independence, public trust and rectitude of judgeship, these concepts as an effective remedy to reduce the impartiality, judicial accountability, and many other pendency of suits.

but crucial issues of today. The most enthralling In part III of the book commenting on the conduct of point of this part is how the author has referred to judges outside/inside the court she quotes Justice findings of foreign judges and legal luminaries and Benjamin Cardozo in the following words “ The

judge even when he is free, is still not wholly free. administration of justice and not aimed with the
He is not to innovate at pleasure. He is not a knight desire for popularity. Under this part author
errant roaming at will in pursuit of his good ideal of enunciates the rectitude of a judge irrelevant of his
beauty or goodness. He is to draw inspiration from place of sitting.
consecrated principles. He is not to yield to Concluding my review this book epitomizes
spasmodic sentiment to vague and unregulated immense experience J. Banumathi has gained over
benevolence. He is to exercise a discretion informed many decades on the bench. This book is thoroughly
by tradition methodized by analogy, disciplined by enjoyable, intensely informative, and would serve as
system and subordinated to the primordial necessity a concise introductory on the judiciary and its
of order in the social life.” By quoting Cardozo she functioning in India. The main theme which runs
wants to articulate that the office of a judge is not across is the responsibilities and duties of a judge and
mere employment in the ordinary sense of the term. a firsthand account of what it is to lead a life of a
The function of a judge must be one dedicated to the judge.